

NOTES

TABLE—DYES I (USED IN NEUTRAL MEDIUM) AND II (USED IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE CONDITION) AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS. VOLUME OF NaCl TAKEN FOR TITRATION : 10 ml

Dye	Concn. of NaCl	Vol. and concn. of AgNO ₃	Drops of indicator	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1N	10.00 ml 0.1N	10	orange-yellow tinged white suspn. → pink ppt.	complete coagulation and clear supernatant liquid at the end point
I	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	8	orange tinged white soln. → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.005N	10.00 ml 0.005N	4	light orange-yellow turbidity → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.004N	10.02 ml 0.004N	4	orange tinged turbid → orange ppt.	coagulation takes place after vigorous shaking and standing.
II	0.1N	10.00 ml 0.1N	10	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation starts 6 drops before the end point but complete coagulation takes place at the end point leaving violet tinged supernatant liquid.
II	0.02N	10.00 ml 0.2N	8	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation at the end point; supernatant liquid almost clear.
II	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	6	pink tinged white suspn. → violet ppt.	coagulation at the end point; supernatant liquid faint violet-pink.
II	0.005N	10.00 ml 0.005N	3	violet shaded white suspn. → violet ppt.	same as above.
II	0.004N	10.02 ml 0.004N	3	same as above.	same as above but coagulation requires vigorous shaking.
II	0.0025N	10.02 ml 0.0025N	3	same as above.	same as above.

That phenolphthalein certainly shows good adsorption properties in slightly alkaline condition, and that dye II is as good as phenolphthalein.

That dye I has the advantage over phenolphthalein and Dye II, that it can be used in neutral as well as in alkaline condition, the former condition being the better.

That dyes III-V, can only be used for solutions of higher concentration; and dyes VI and VII are unsuitable as adsorption indicators.

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, *Current Sci. (India)*, 1947, **16**, 254; *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, **42**, 1148.
2. E. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976 (accepted).
3. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 676.

Preparation and Characterisation of α -Chloro- β -(3:4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid

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α -HALO- β -PHENYL substituted acrylic acids are usually obtained by the methods of Sudborough and Thompson¹ and Sudborough and James². The isolation and characterisation of methyl- $[\alpha$ -chloro-

β -3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl]-acrylate (II) was reported by the author³. In the present communication the preparation of the acid (I) is reported. Thus α -halo- β -phenyl substituted acids are now accessible by a new route.

Darzens glycidic ester condensation of piperonal with methyl chloroacetate in presence of methanolic sodium methoxide afforded the compound (II) which was hydrolysed to give its sodium salt (III).

- (I), R = H
 (II), R = CH₃
 (III), R = Na.

The sodium salt was smoothly converted to the acid (I) by acidification. The new compound (I) was characterised by analytical and spectroscopic methods.

The compound responded to Beilstein test for chlorine. The vinylic chlorine resisted hydrolysis. The mass spectrum of the compound, (C₁₀H₇O₄Cl) displayed the molecular ion at m/e 226 and the peak at m/e 228 was approximately one-third of the molecular ion peak. The nmr spectrum showed the absence of the methyl proton signals when compared with that of the ester. The carboxylic proton was

not seen being far down field. The ν C=O of carboxylic group, as expected, was at 1690 cm^{-1} in the i.r. spectrum, whereas it was at 1730 cm^{-1} in the case of the methyl ester.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Kofler hot stage m.p. apparatus and are uncorrected. Chlorine analysis was done by oxygen flask method. I.R. spectrum was taken on Unicam SP 1000 infra red spectrophotometer. NMR was recorded on Varian A-60 NMR-spectrophotometer (TMS as internal reference). Mass spectrum was taken on A.E.I. mass spectrometer, model MS9.

Methyl-(α -Chloro- β -3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate (II)

A solution of 54.0 g. (1.8 mols) of piperonal and 47.4 ml. (2.7 mols) of methyl chloroacetate were slowly added under stirring to 12.42 g. (2.7 g atoms) sodium in 180 ml. dry methanol chilled to -10° in an ice salt bath. The addition of the mixture was complete in 3 hr. The stirring was continued for another 2 hr at -5° and then left overnight at room temperature. The mixture was poured into ice water (700 ml) containing acetic acid (4 ml). The white crystalline solid separated was collected, washed with cold water and dried in vacuum dessicator, yield nearly 90%. The crude dry powder was dissolved by boiling in a large volume of petroleum ether (b.p. 60° - 80°). The clear solution was decanted and allowed to cool overnight inside a refrigerator. Out of the two types of crystals formed, only the bunches of flaky needles adhering to the sides were collected and the lumpy crystalline solids of the epoxy ester at the bottom of the flask were not taken out. The flaky needles were recrystallised to give the colourless needles of methyl-(α -chloro- β -3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate (II), m.p. 136° (lit.³ 136°); yield 50%; Found: C, 54.91; H, 3.86; Cl, 14.65%; Calc. for $C_{11}H_9O_4Cl$: C, 54.88; H, 3.74; Cl, 14.76%.

α -Chloro- β -(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid (I)

The above methyl ester (II) (5 g.), sodium hydroxide (25 ml., 2N) was boiled till the compound completely dissolved. On cooling the solution, the sodium salt (III) separated out and collected, yield nearly 85%. The sodium salt was then suspended in water and acidified with hydrochloric acid to afford a solid product which was collected, washed with water and dried. On recrystallising from aqueous alcohol afforded the stout prismatic crystals of α -chloro- β -(3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylic acid (I), m.p. 220° , yield about 65%. The compound responded to Beilstein test for chlorine. Found: C, 53.50; H, 3.24; Cl, 15.37%. $C_{10}H_7O_4Cl$ requires: C, 52.98; H, 3.09; Cl, 15.48%. I.R. $\nu_{\text{Max}}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1690 cm^{-1} (S) (Carboxylic C=O); 1610 cm^{-1} (M) (Ar C=C). NMR (DMSO) 6.15δ (S, 2H, -O-CH₂-O-); 7.05δ (d, 1H, Ar C-5 proton, $J_{\text{Ortho}} = 7.50$ Cps); 7.50δ (poorly resolved, appearing as d, 1H, Ar C-6 proton, $J_{\text{Ortho}} = 7.50$ Cps; $J_{\text{Meta}} = 0.8$ Cps); 7.60δ (S with slight bifurcation and

overlapped with C-6 proton signal, 1H, Ar C-2 proton, $J_{\text{Meta}} = 0.8$ Cps); 7.90δ (S, 1H, vinylic proton). Mass spectrum: The mass spectrum of the compound revealed the characteristic abundance ratio of M and M+2 peaks in 3 : 1, corresponding to Cl^{35} and Cl^{37} . Significant fragments occurred at m/e 228 (M+2, 30%), 226 (M+, base peak), 190 (M-HCl, 80%), 121 (M-HCl, -C₂-COOH, 80%).

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References

1. J. J. SUDBOROUGH and K. J. THOMPSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 666.
2. J. J. SUDBOROUGH and T. C. JAMES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, **89**, 105.
3. S. P. DHOUBHADEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 146.

Synthesis of 1, 2-disubstituted-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydro-4-quinazoline thiones

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HUNIG and Hubner¹ have reported that reaction of benzoyl isothiocyanate with 1-morpholino-1-cyclohexane gives benzoxazine-4-thione derivatives. Carney *et al.*² reported that 1,3-benzoxazine-4-thiones undergo reaction with aromatic amines giving quinazoline-thiones. However, in a three component system—1-morpholinocyclohexane, benzoyl isothiocyanate and arylamine—direct formation of the same quinazoline thione has limitations—thiourea being the major product. Solvent used in these condensations is of vital importance. Benzene or ethanol gives mainly thiourea. If tetrahydrofuran is used as a solvent the major product is quinazoline thione. This suggests that the intermediate formed must be an adduct which then cyclises to quinazoline derivative or first intermediate is 1,2-cyclo addition product—oxazine thione—which further undergoes reaction with arylamine to quinazoline thiones. Both these possibilities are confirmed by the fact that benzoxazines can be converted to quinazoline thiones. Benzoyl isothiocyanate was condensed with anilino cyclohexene in ether and the adduct obtained when refluxed in tetrahydrofuran afforded

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